

Soft toffees “White Rabbit Creamy Candies” contaminated with melamine from China are not safe

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More than 54,000 infants fell sick in China in conjunction with milk powder contaminated with melamine according to reports from the health authorities there. Almost 40,000 babies, who were mainly fed on milk powder, were treated in outpatient centres and around 13,000 infants were hospitalised, 104 with serious symptoms. Three children have died so far of kidney failure. The control authorities in Germany have examined composite food imported from China for melamine. In Baden-Württemberg the authorities detected high melamine levels in a sample of soft toffees (“White Rabbit Creamy Candies”) from China. Melamine is normally used to make synthetic resins. In China the substance was clearly used to fake a high protein level in food.

Against this backdrop the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) has assessed whether consumption of the soft toffees “White Rabbit Creamy Candies” with the confirmed high melamine level (152 mg/kg) constitutes a risk to health. The Institute has established that consumption of seven contaminated soft toffees a day in the age group of 1 to 3 years and consumption of a quarter to half a bag (12-24) of these soft toffees by children over the age of three would lead to an exceeding of the tolerable daily intake of melamine. In its assessment BfR comes to the conclusion that, in the case of comparatively high consumption of products of this kind with the above-mentioned levels of melamine over a longer period, damage to health is possible.

The full version of this BfR Opinion is available in German on http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/208/mit_melamin_belastete_weichkaramellen_white_rabbit_creamy_candies_aus_china_sind_nicht_sicher.pdf